

ISic0409

I.Sicily inscription 0409

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

museum inventory states 'prov. incerta'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 238

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Dis · Mañib(us) ·
2. C(aius) · Iulîus · Pñiñio
3. Isidis · scopâr(ius)
4. vix(it) · ann(os) · LXXX
5. pie · salve

Apparatus

Text transcribed from photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491620

EDCS 21900451

Bibliography

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Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014

Museum archive photograph